

AGU Fall Meeting

San Francisco 12-16 December 2016

Persistent Identifiers: a Prerequisite to Establish the Framework for Scholarly Link Exchange - Scholix

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SCHOLIX

<http://scholix.org>

Objectives

- Increase visibility & discoverability of data & articles
- Place data in context to enable re-use
- Support credit attribution mechanisms

Publishers

Repositories

Data Centers

Publishers

SCHOLIX

Repositories

Data Centers

Link

Link Information Package

Publication Date

Link Publisher

Link Provider

Relationship Type

Source Object

Identifier

Object Type

Title

Author

Publication Date

Publisher

Target Object

Identifier

Object Type

Title

Author

Publication Date

Publisher

Scholix Prerequisite: Persistent Identification

Identifier

ID: 10.1007/s10236-011-0476-6
ID Schema: DOI

Author Identifier

ID: 0000-0001-5492-3212
ID Schema: ORCID

SCHOLIX

... in practice

Roughness length along a transect in the Jade Bay, 2008, supplement to: Lefebvre, Alice; Ernstsén, Verner Brandbyge; Winter, Christian (2011):

[Influence of compound bedforms on hydraulic roughness in a tidal environment. Ocean Dynamics, 61\(12\), 2201-2210](#)

Typology:	dataset
Identifier:	10.1594/pangaea.775828
Identifier type:	doi
Author(s):	Lefebvre, Alice, Ernstsén, Verner Brandbyge, Winter, Christian,
Date:	2008-04-17T05:33:00/2008-04-17T17:01:00

provenance (of this object):	Date Of Collection	Action
	2015-12-13	Full Metadata collected from Datasets in DataCite
	2015-12-14	Full Metadata collected from PANGAEA

[LINK TO DATASETS](#)
[LINK TO PUBLICATIONS](#)
[OTHER LINKS](#)

["Influence of compound bedforms on hydraulic roughness in a tidal environment"]

[Lefebvre Alice, Ernstsén Verner B, Winter Christian,](#)

PID : 10.1007/s10236-011-0476-6

PID Type : doi

provenance (of this link):	Date Of Collection	Datasource	Action
	2016-01-04	System Deduction	Typology of target object derived by the system
	2015-12-14	PANGAEA	Relation collected from PANGAEA
	2015-12-13	Datasets in DataCite	Relation collected from Datasets in DataCite

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▼<oai:OAI-PMH xmlns:oai="http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/ http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/OAI-PMH.xsd">
  <oai:responseDate>2016-12-10T13:06:09Z</oai:responseDate>
  ▶<oai:request verb="GetRecord" identifier="oai:dnet:3c253311d1401b3992ee484e3ef288d9" metadataPrefix="dli">...</oai:request>
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    ▼<oai:record>
      ▶<oai:header>...</oai:header>
      ▼<oai:metadata>
        ▼<dli:dliObject xmlns:dli="http://dli.service.research-infrastructures.eu" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
xsi:schemaLocation="http://dli.service.research-infrastructures.eu http://dli.service.research-infrastructures.eu/res/DLIFMetadataFormat.xsd">
          <dli:dnetResourceIdentifier>3c253311d1401b3992ee484e3ef288d9</dli:dnetResourceIdentifier>
          <dli:originalIdentifier type="doi" resolvedUrl="http://dx.doi.org/10.1594/pangaea.775828">10.1594/pangaea.775828</dli:originalIdentifier>
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              <dli:entitytype>publication</dli:entitytype>
              <dli:pid type="doi">10.1007/s10236-011-0476-6</dli:pid>
              <dli:typeOfRelation>IsSupplementTo</dli:typeOfRelation>
              ▶<dli:title>...</dli:title>
              ▶<dli:authors>...</dli:authors>
              ▶<dli:relationProvenance>...</dli:relationProvenance>
            </dli:relation>
          </dli:relations>
        </dli:dliObject>
      </oai:metadata>
    </oai:record>
  </oai:GetRecord>
</oai:OAI-PMH>
```


Roughness length along a transect in the Jade Bay, 2008, supplement to: Lefebvre, Alice; Ernstsen, Verner Brandbyge; Winter, Christian (2011): Influence of compound bedforms on hydraulic roughness in a tidal environment. *Ocean Dynamics*, 61(12), 2201-2210

Alice Lefebvre, Verner Brandbyge Ernstsen & Christian Winter

Supplementary dataset published 2011 via PANGAEA - Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science

This dataset consists of average water depth, average current velocity and direction and roughness lengths calculated from the spatially-averaged velocity profiles collected with an ADCP along a transect in the Jade Bay in 2008.

<https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.775828> Cite

Relations ^①

Contributions ^②

Influence of compound bedforms on hydraulic roughness in a tidal environment

Work published August 7, 2011

Is supplemented by <http://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.775828>

DataCite (Crossref)

<http://doi.org/10.1007/S10236-011-0476-6> Cite

Outlook

- Proposal for Scholix schema
 - Possibly in JSON-LD
 - Using schema.org vocabulary (e.g. <http://schema.org/Dataset>)
- Participation
 - Feed link information to existing Scholix hub
 - Become a hub
 - Develop third-party services
 - Help developing the guidelines

Acknowledgements

- Adrian Burton, Australian National Data Service
- Amir Aryani, Australian National Data Service
- Hylke Koers, Elsevier
- Markus Stocker, PANGAEA
- Martin Fenner, DataCite
- Michael Diepenbroek, PANGAEA
- Paolo Manghi, Institute of Information Science and Technology
- Sandro La Bruzzo, Institute of Information Science and Technology
- Uwe Schindler, PANGAEA
- Wouter Haak, Elsevier
- & RDA/WDS Publishing Data Services WG!

Conclusion

- Interoperability of literature-data link information
- Hubs collect link information from communities
- Hubs share standardized link information
- Link information more easily globally visible
- Unambiguous identification is crucial

Influence of compound bedforms on hydraulic roughness in a tidal environment

Typology:	publication
Identifier:	10.1007/s10236-011-0476-6
Identifier type:	doi
Author(s):	Lefebvre Alice,Ernstsen Verner B.,Winter Christian,
Date:	2011-08-06T12:46:05Z

	Date Of Collection	Action
provenance (of this object):	2015-12-13	Object PID collected from Datasets in DataCite
	2015-12-14	Object PID collected from PANGAEA
	2016-01-04	Full-metadata record collected from CrossRef

[LINK TO DATASETS](#)
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